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ON CONTRADICTIONS DETERMINED BY THE CHOICE OF THE CONDITION OF CRACKING

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Annotation: This paper examines a well-known solution to the elastoplastic problem of a rapidly rotating circular disk, which presents results that contradict general notions about the distribution of plastic deformations. It also addresses issues arising from the application of piecewise-linear yield conditions in the case of plane stress. The discussion highlights the inconsistencies and theoretical challenges associated with such modeling approaches.

Keywords: elastoplastic problem, rapidly rotating disk, plastic strain, piecewise-linear yield conditions

О ПРОТИВОРЕЧИЯХ, ОПРЕДЕЛЯЕМЫХ ВЫБОРОМ УСЛОВИЯ ТРЕЩИНООБРАЗОВАНИЯ

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Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается известное решение упругопластической задачи быстро вращающегося круглого диска, в котором представлены результаты, противоречащие общим представлениям о распределении пластических деформаций. В ней также рассматриваются вопросы, возникающие при применении кусочно-линейных условий текучести в случае плоского напряжения.

В обсуждении подчеркиваются несоответствия и теоретические проблемы, связанные с такими подходами к моделированию.

Ключевые слова: упругопластическая задача, быстро вращающийся диск, пластическая деформация, кусочно-линейные условия текучести

Piecewise-linear yield conditions make it possible, in certain cases, to obtain exact or approximate analytical solutions, whereas smooth yield conditions allow only for numerical solutions to the problem [1]. Despite the problems caused by the presence of singular points, piecewise-linear yield conditions are quite frequently considered in the mathematical theory of plasticity [2-4]. The appeal of choosing piecewise-linear yield conditions lies in the possibility of obtaining analytical solutions to certain problems [5-8].

Stress–strain state of a rotating elastoplastic disk under Tresca condition

Within the framework of plastic flow theory, the following relations hold for a rapidly rotating circular disk:

- stresses in the plastic zone $0 \leq \rho \leq c$ ([1]):

$$\sigma_\rho = 2k - \frac{1}{3}m\rho^2, \sigma_\theta = 2k; \quad (1)$$

- elastic strains in the plastic zone:

$$E\varepsilon_r^e = 2k(1 - \nu) - \frac{1}{3}m\rho^2, E\varepsilon_\theta^e = 2k(1 - \nu) + \frac{\nu}{3}m\rho^2, E\varepsilon_z^e = \frac{\nu}{3}m\rho^2 - 4k\nu; \quad (2)$$

- • plastic strains:

$$E\varepsilon_r^p = 0, E\varepsilon_\theta^p = -\frac{1+3\nu}{9}m\rho^2, E\varepsilon_z^p = \frac{1+3\nu}{9}m\rho^2; \quad (3)$$

- displacements and strains in the plastic zone:

$$Eu = 2k(1 - \nu)\rho - \frac{1}{9}m\rho^3, E\varepsilon_r = 2k(1 - \nu) - \frac{1}{3}m\rho^2, \quad (4)$$

$$E\varepsilon_\theta = 2k(1 - \nu) - \frac{1}{9}m\rho^2, E\varepsilon_z = \frac{1+6\nu}{9}m\rho^2 - 4k\nu;$$

– stresses in the elastic zone $c \leq \rho \leq 1$ (the solution is obtained with regard to the stress continuity conditions at the elastoplastic boundary $\rho = c$)

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_\rho &= 2k + \frac{(1+3\nu)m}{24} \left(\left(2 - \frac{c^2}{\rho^2} \right) c^2 - 3 \frac{\nu+3}{1+3\nu} \rho^2 \right); \\ \sigma_\theta &= 2k + \frac{(1+3\nu)m}{24} \left(\left(2 + \frac{c^2}{\rho^2} \right) c^2 - 3\rho^2 \right); \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

– strains and displacements in the elastic zone

$$\begin{aligned} E\varepsilon_\rho &= 2k(1-\nu) + \frac{m}{24} \left(2c^2(1+2\nu-3\nu^2) - 9(1-\nu^2)\rho^2 - \frac{(1+4\nu+3\nu^2)c^4}{\rho^2} \right); \\ E\varepsilon_\theta &= 2k(1-\nu) + \frac{m}{24} \left(2c^2(1+2\nu-3\nu^2) - 3(1-\nu^2)\rho^2 - \frac{(1+4\nu+3\nu^2)c^4}{\rho^2} \right); \\ Eu &= 2k(1-\nu)\rho + \frac{m}{24} \left(2c^2(1+2\nu-3\nu^2)\rho - 3(1-\nu^2)\rho^2 + \frac{(1+4\nu+3\nu^2)c^4}{\rho^2} \right); \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here, $\rho = r/b$ is the dimensionless radial coordinate, b is the outer radius of the disk, $m = \gamma\omega^2 b^2/g$ is a dimensionless parameter, ω is the angular velocity, γ is the specific weight, g is the acceleration due to gravity, E is Young’s modulus, and ν is Poisson’s ratio.

If the stresses in the elastic zone are not determined from the original problem but instead by solving a boundary value problem—using the continuity condition of radial stress at the elastoplastic boundary $[\sigma_\rho(\rho = c)] = 0$ and the boundary condition at the outer edge $\sigma_\rho(\rho = 1) = -p$ —then different formulas for stresses and strains are obtained.

To solve equation (5), the boundary condition $\sigma_\rho(\rho = 1) = -p$ yields the following relation:

$$m = \frac{24(2k-p)}{3(\nu+3)b^4 + (1+3\nu)(c^2-2b^2)c^2}, \quad m = \frac{\gamma}{g} \frac{\omega^2 b^2}{k} \tag{7}$$

Alternatively, expressing $c = c(m)$ as a function of m (with the sign in the solution of the biquadratic equation (7) chosen based on physical reasoning: as the angular velocity ω increases, the radius of the elastoplastic boundary increases), we obtain:

$$c = \sqrt{b^2 - 2\sqrt{2}b \sqrt{\frac{6km+3mp-b^2m^2}{(1+3\nu)m^2}}}. \tag{8}$$

If the pressure on the outer boundary of the disk is $p = 0$, then formula (7) takes the form given in [1].

In the theory of elastoplastic bodies, if the natural state hypothesis is adopted (i.e., the body has no irreversible deformations prior to loading), then the plastic strains at the elastoplastic boundary must be zero. However, the circumferential component of the plastic strain tensor given by equation

(3) is zero only at the point $\rho = 0$, while at the elastoplastic boundary $\rho = c$ it takes the value $E\varepsilon_{\theta}^p = -\frac{1+3\nu}{9}mc^2 \neq 0$.

Therefore, displacements and all strain components (except for the radial component) exhibit discontinuities at the elastoplastic boundary. The continuity of the radial strain component at this boundary is due to the continuity of the stress tensor components and the fact that the radial component of the plastic strain is zero at this interface.

An analysis of the elastic solution shows that the maximum value of the yield function occurs at the center of the disk, where $\sigma_{\rho} = \sigma_{\theta}$; that is, plastic deformation begins at the point $\rho = 0$ in the case of the singular Tresca plasticity regime

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{\theta} - \sigma_z = 2k, \\ \sigma_{\rho} - \sigma_z = 2k. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

However, the plasticity regime (9) cannot be realized in a region containing the point $\rho = 0$, as it contradicts the equilibrium equation (substituting (9) into the equilibrium equation yields $\sigma_{\rho} - \sigma_{\theta} + m\rho^2 = 0$, $\sigma_{\rho}, \sigma_{\theta} = \text{const}$).

On the initiation of the plastic zone in a rapidly rotating disk

Considering piecewise-linear yield conditions as an approximation of the "true" yield condition, we take the von Mises criterion as the "true" yield condition for an isotropic material—although this choice is not essential.

In a rotating disk, inertial forces induce positive radial stresses. The application of compressive pressure p on the outer boundary of the disk alters the stress distribution within the rotating disk. Varying the two parameters ω and p may lead to the initiation of a plastic zone either at the center of the disk or at its outer boundary.

If $p < 1$, the von Mises yield function in the elastic region reaches its maximum at $\rho = 0$. In this case, the plastic zone will initiate at the center of the disk.

If $p = 1$ and $m = 0$, the entire disk reaches the limit state. Analysis of the von Mises yield function in the elastic state shows that a plastic zone may initiate at the outer boundary $\rho = b$ if the external pressure $p > 1$ and $m < \frac{32(1+\nu)}{(7+2\nu+7\nu^2)b^2}$.

Plastic deformation at the outer boundary also occurs when

$$m = \frac{32(1+\nu)}{(7+2\nu+7\nu^2)b^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p_b = \frac{14\nu+5-3\nu^2}{7+2\nu+7\nu^2}.$$

This option ($p > 1$) is possible if the pressure arises due to the automatic fastening of the disks and changes during their rotation.

Stress and strain state of a rapidly rotating elastic-plastic disk

From the solution to the problem of the elastic state of a circular disk, it follows that at the center of the disk, $\sigma_\rho = \sigma_\theta$. This conclusion also results from the equilibrium equation, assuming that $d\frac{d\sigma_\rho}{d\rho}\Big|_{\rho=0} \neq \infty$. Due to the continuity of stresses across the elastic–plastic boundary, this equality implies that in the plastic zone, at the point $\rho = 0$, the mode of the piecewise-linear yield condition must be realized in such a way that the corresponding side of the yield polygon intersects the line $\sigma_\rho = \sigma_\theta$.

Let us consider a piecewise-linear yield condition of the general form:

$$\alpha\sigma_\theta + \beta\sigma_\rho = 2. \tag{10}$$

For regime (10), the stress distribution takes the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_\rho &= \frac{2k}{\alpha + \beta} - \frac{\alpha m \rho^2}{3\alpha + \beta} + C\rho^{-\frac{\alpha+\beta}{\alpha}}, \\ \sigma_\theta &= \frac{2k}{\alpha + \beta} - \frac{\beta m \rho^2}{3\alpha + \beta} - \frac{\beta}{\alpha} C\rho^{-\frac{\alpha+\beta}{\alpha}}. \end{aligned}$$

The plasticity regime corresponding to the case $\alpha = 0, \beta = 1$ cannot be realized. Substituting into the equilibrium equation yields: $\sigma_\rho = 2k, \sigma_\theta = 2k + m\rho^2$.

This solution leads to the stress vector exceeding the yield surface, as $\sigma_\theta > 2k$.

Since for all plasticity regimes that can be realized in the vicinity of the point $\rho = 0$, the condition $(\alpha + \beta)/\alpha > 0$ holds, it follows that the constant $C = 0$. Therefore, in the plastic zone:

$$\sigma_\rho = \frac{2k}{\alpha+\beta} - \frac{\alpha m \rho^2}{3\alpha+\beta}, \quad \sigma_\theta = \frac{2k}{\alpha+\beta} - \frac{\beta m \rho^2}{3\alpha+\beta}. \tag{11}$$

Within the framework of plastic flow theory, if the plastic strains are zero prior to loading, then:

$$\alpha\varepsilon_\rho^p = \beta\varepsilon_\theta^p. \tag{12}$$

Taking into account equations (11) and (12), the displacement in the plastic zone is governed by the following equation:

$$E \left(\alpha \frac{du_\rho}{d\rho} - \beta \frac{u_\rho}{\rho} \right) + \frac{2(1-\nu)(\beta-\alpha)k}{\alpha+\beta} + \frac{2\alpha\beta\nu + 2 + \alpha^2}{3\alpha+\beta} m\rho^2 = 0.$$

Solving this equation, we find:

$$Eu = -\frac{2\alpha\beta\nu + 2 + \alpha^2}{3\alpha+\beta} m\rho^3 - \frac{2(1-\nu)k}{\alpha+\beta} + C\rho^{\frac{\beta}{\alpha}}. \quad (13)$$

The plastic strains corresponding to the displacement field (13) and the stress field (11) are given by the following formulas:

$$E\varepsilon_\rho^p = -\frac{\beta(3\alpha\nu + \beta\nu + 3\beta)}{(3\alpha+\beta)(3\alpha-\beta)} m\rho^2 + \frac{\beta}{\alpha} C\rho^{\frac{\beta-\alpha}{\alpha}}, \quad (14)$$

$$E\varepsilon_\theta^p = -\frac{\alpha(3\alpha\nu + \beta\nu + 3\beta)}{(3\alpha+\beta)(3\alpha-\beta)} m\rho^2 + C\rho^{\frac{\beta-\alpha}{\alpha}}.$$

Plasticity regimes with $\alpha < \beta$ cannot be realized, as they lead to the stress vector exceeding the yield surface. If $\beta < \alpha$, then due to the boundedness of plastic strains, the constant C in formulas (14) must be set to zero. However, in this case, the plastic strains will never be zero at the elastic-plastic boundary.

The plasticity regime that does not lead to contradictions is $\alpha = \beta = 1$, corresponding to the condition $\sigma_\theta + \sigma_\rho = 2k$. For this regime, the following holds:

$$E\varepsilon_\rho^p = E\varepsilon_\theta^p = -\frac{(3\nu+\nu+4)}{8} m\rho^2 + C.$$

From the condition that the plastic strains vanish at the elastic-plastic boundary $\rho = c$, it follows that $C = \frac{(3\nu+\nu+4)}{8} mc^2$. Therefore, $E\varepsilon_\rho^p = E\varepsilon_\theta^p = -\frac{(3\nu+\nu+4)}{8} m\rho^2$.

Thus, the incorrect result regarding the strains can be explained by the fact that, in the case of plane stress, the Tresca hexagon poorly approximates the "true" yield surface when the nonzero principal stresses are equal. A correct result is obtained when the Schmidt yield criterion is used instead.

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